

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF THROUGH THE THICKNESS TEMPERATURE GRADIENTS IN THICK COMPOSITES DURING INFUSION PROCESS

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SUMMARY

Temperature gradients in thick composite parts produced with non-isothermal infusion techniques are investigated through different series of tests reproducing the most common configurations of non-isothermal infusion setups. Results show a real variation of temperature through the thickness that justifies the need for three-dimensional simulation to completely reproduce the phenomena.

Keywords: Thermoset composites, resin infusion, non-isothermal infusion, temperature gradient

INTRODUCTION

Vacuum bagging techniques are becoming a fairly common technique for the production of ever bigger and thicker parts in high performance applications, such as wing panels, competition boat hulls or wind turbine blades. The production of such big parts implies in most cases an increase in component thickness, which represents a challenge for the numerical tools for the simulation of the infusion [1], specially when used to simulate residual stress behaviour due to temperature gradients through the thickness as a result of the convection of the resin during the filling stage.. Although flow simulations and structural analysis programs can solve for variables in 3D, the solution of the temperature through the thickness of the part during the filling has remained a challenge due to the heat dispersion and resin convection in plane [2-4]

Apart from simulation tools, most current production strategies are also optimized towards providing fast infusion strategies of shell-type components. A thickness increase thus implies a need to modify the established infusion scheme and workflow setup in order to accommodate adequate infusion of a thick, 3D shape, without dry spots

in a reasonable amount of time. Several alternative strategies have been implemented to ensure a faster and better flow front advance in thick 3D components, such as the use of race-tracking channels and sequential gating, the inclusion of high permeability layers or the introduction of a heat source in the system.

The latter option is common practice due to its proven effect of resin viscosity reduction, which can be described by exponential laws, such as the one presented in equation 1[5]:

$$\eta(\alpha, T) = A_0 \cdot e^{B_0 \alpha} \cdot e^{-\frac{A+B\alpha}{RT}} \quad (\text{eq.1})$$

In the above equation, viscosity (η) is presented as a function of degree of curing (α), temperature (T), and A_0 , A, B_0 and B are specific coefficients of the equation and liquid specific coefficients that must be adjusted experimentally for each resin

Viscosity decrease can be directly related to a decrease in injection fill time; consequently, bigger parts can be infused for the same pot life of the resin.

In a vacuum bagging infusion scheme, the heat source can be introduced either by controlled heating of the rigid mould or by pre-heating the resin. For small parts geometries, heating the mould presents an easy and homogeneous way to introduce heat into the system. For geometrically complex parts (and moulds), bringing the complete mould to a homogeneous temperature becomes a challenging and sometimes an impossible task. In such cases, resin heating is the more suitable and sometimes the only viable option.

To date, non-isothermal simulations of the infusion process of a composite part can be conducted to solve two-dimensional temperature problems [6], supposing as an initial condition that the reinforcement preform has a assumed parabolic temperature profile through the thickness. However, in thick composite parts produced with non-isothermal infusion techniques, the assumption of a temperature profile through the thickness of the part during the infusion process may no be valid. A three-dimensional model capable of predict a temperature gradient through the thickness of the preform during the infusion process required [2-5]. An experimental study will allow us understand the uncertainty when making assumptions about the temperature profile.

AIM AND METHODOLOGY

The experimental plan presented here has as an objective to determine the validity of such a simplified temperature map. The work also aims to investigate the relevance of temperature gradient through the thickness of the specimen. That would confirm the suspected need to enhance the current information obtained from 2D simulations by turning efforts to 3D simulations that do take the impact of the third dimension of thick specimens into account.

The objective of the tests conducted is to evaluate the evolution of the temperature gradients occurring in the production process of thick composite laminates. Those gradients are caused due to the introduction of a heat source in the system, either by heating the resin or by heating the mould, hereby causing variations in temperature in the flow front advance direction (longitudinal axis of the specimen, Figure 1) and also through the thickness of it as the flow front advances. In addition to these heat sources, the curing of the resin which is an exothermic reaction will itself be a heat source but is not addressed in this work.

Setup description

An infusion setup has been designed to evaluate the temperature variations through the thickness of a flat thick reinforcement preform during the infusion process. In order to evaluate the influence of a heat source on the viscosity of the resin and temperature conditions, two different heat sources are available in the setup. The first one is an aluminium plate with a heat control system used to introduce a heat into the system from the mould (T4). The second possibility is heating the resin just before the infusion (T3). In this way, the system can reproduce the two more common systems of introducing heat in real production systems. An schematic of the setup can be observed in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Schematic of the experimental setup.

To control the infusion process parameters, pressure restrictors are used to ensure a constant pressure injection configuration, which is supplied by a vacuum pump. The resin entrance is placed in one side of the specimen, where a plastic diffuser ensures the correct distribution of the resin through all the specimen width. In this way, the gate configuration corresponds to that of a linear infusion configuration.

To evaluate the temperature, during the infusion process, the temperature is monitored through different control points located at different longitudinal and through-the-thickness locations of the specimen (Figure 1, control section detail). In this way, both

the longitudinal and through the thickness variation of the temperature can be captured. Sets of thermocouples were embedded in the dry fibre preform, in three different sections of the longitudinal axis of the specimen. Each section include four register points, corresponding to the mould surface, middle plain, quarter of thickness and three quarters of the thickness of the specimen. Moreover, an infrared camera was placed on top of the setup to record the temperature variation and also to correlate the flow front with the temperature and the thermal evolution.

Test description

With the aim to understand different physics effects involved in the temperature evolution during infusion and cure, three different infusion scenarios were planned. These are: mould heating infusion, resin pre-heating infusion and room temperature infusion. Table 1 summarises the characteristics for each of the three infusion processes.

Table 1 Summary of the entire experimental plan conducted.

	Heat Source	Repetitions	Material	Temperature recording points (+ camera on top)
Set 1	None	3	Epoxy and Fibreglass	12 on preform
Set 2	Resin	3	Epoxy and Fibreglass	12 on preform + mould+ resin
Set 3	Mould	3	Epoxy and Fibreglass	12 on preform + mould

In the first set of tests, and with the aim to evaluate the cure kinetics effect, specimens were infused with all the different elements involved in the system at room temperature. As no heat source is introduced into the system, the results in that test can be used to separate the temperature rise due to exothermic cure reaction.

In the second batch of tests, the resin is pre-heated in an oven in order to achieve a pre-set temperature. During the infusion process the temperature of the resin is also monitored by using a thermocouple into the mixing pot, in order to ensure that its temperature does not differ significantly from the preset temperature. The mould, as well as the preform, remained at room temperature, creating a system with the same temperature at each side of the mould, and leaving the temperature gradient evolution between the two sides of the mould to the conductivity and convective coefficients of both sides.

In the last set of tests, the mould is set as a temperature source for the system. The preform is pre-heated in an oven to a temperature in a mid point between the room temperature and the mould. Resin is injected at room temperature, creating a system with a temperature difference between the resin and the preform and also between both sides of the mould, simulating a fully complex and close to real production system situation.

Epoxy resin and multidirectional fibreglass fabric were used to conduct all the experiments. The lay-up of reinforcement fabric was that of a quasi-isotropic configuration to ensure a flow front advance as homogeneous as possible.

Due to the amount of experimental data and the complexity in the analysis and discussion of this data, only the results for the third set of tests will be discussed and evaluated in this work. Table 2 summarises the specimen dimensions and pre-set temperatures during the tests conducted for the second set of experiments.

Table 2: Dimensions and temperature description for the third test setup.

Specimen Length	250 mm	Mould temperature	70°C
Specimen width	150 mm	Room temperature (bag side, resin)	20°C
Specimen thickness	30 mm	Preform temperature	40°C

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Results data

Recorded temperature at different locations of the specimen is shown in Figure 2 for the first specimen. For simplicity, only the results for this specimen are shown. The results for the other two specimens are similar and hence are not presented due to page limitation of this presentation. The different thermocouples are identified by its relative position in the thickness and longitudinal directions in the specimen. For instance, H0 indicates that the sensor was placed at the mould level while H3 indicates that the sensor was located at $\frac{3}{4}$ of the thickness of the specimen. For the longitudinal direction, sensors were labelled from S1 to S3 depending on their relative position from the resin inlet.

Figure 2: Evolution of the temperature during all the process for specimen #1.

From the entire time domain, the infusion stage is isolated to be analyzed separately, obtaining the plot presented in Figure 3. As observed in the figure, for each section the variation of the temperature is different depending on the location of the sensor in the thickness of the preform. Moreover, the temperature registered by most of the sensors increases once the resin flow has reached their location.

Figure 3: Evolution of the temperature during the infusion stage for specimen #1.

The temperature evolution is also contrasted with the infusion profile from the infrared camera that can be observed in Figure 4. This temperature profile adds an extra control point corresponding to the top surface of the specimen, in contact with the vacuum bag, at room temperature.

Figure 4: Thermal imaging of the infusion of specimen #1 when the flow front reaches section 2. Resin flow advance direction is from left to right. Temperature scale is in °C.

RESULTS DISCUSSION

Expected results

To better understand the behaviour of the temperature evolution during the test, the test was reproduced numerically before being conducted. The simulation work was realized within LIMS software environment. LIMS is an academic code (University of Delaware) [7-10] that allows for the modelling of injection moulding processes and can give an approach of the expected temperatures during the resin infusion process using the 2D thermal solutions implemented. The software assumes that the thermal equilibrium is obtained as soon as the resin reaches the fabric, causing a fast temperature variation in the control point. These have been proved as a good approach for thin laminates in double sided rigid tool configurations.

The configuration selected for the experimental tests implies the infusion of the resin at a colder temperature than the preform surrounded by a mould at high temperature and a vacuum bag at room temperature. Consequently, the expected temperature variation depends on the heat transfer between the resin and the preform, which in turn is affected by different boundary conditions of the sides of the mould. It can be anticipated that in the midplane of the specimen, the control point situated in the first control section should record the larger temperature variation and be the coolest point of the specimen as all the resin have to go through that point. For the same reason, the last control point

should be the hottest control point as the smaller quantity of resin that arrives to this point has absorbed heat from the preform. The central section in the length of the specimen should have an intermediate behaviour. Figure 5 summarises the results of a simulation reproducing the experimental work using average values for the properties of the fabric and the resin, where it can be clearly seen this tendency in temperature variation. In the figure, each control point is located at the midplane of sections 1, 2 and 3 of the longitudinal axis of the specimen (see Figure 2).

Figure 5: Expected results from currently available simulation capability.

Discussion

To better understand its behaviour, the evolution of the temperature in the mid-plane of the specimen is shown in Figure 6. In experiments, a non expected behaviour is observed in thermocouples corresponding to the second and third section, where an increase in temperature instead of the expected decrease due to the effect of the cool resin entering into a hot environment is recorded.

This behaviour is confirmed by the thermal evolution observed from the thermal imaging (Figure 4), where the resin, initially supposed cold, became hotter than the preform during the infusion. The temperature seen on the dry side (right) is lower than the initially assumed. This suggests that, due to the presence of the vacuum bag at room temperature in one side, there is a temperature gradient in the reinforcement preform before it is impregnated by the resin. It can be also assumed that this gradient is more important for thicker preforms.

For the values recorded on the second and third thermocouples, a monotonic temperature increase is observed as soon as the resin reaches these points. This monotonic increase without a flat zone or plateau may indicate that the heat released from the exothermic cure of the resin is influencing the evolution of the temperature.

Figure 7: Temperature evolution at midplane during infusion period.

CONCLUSIONS

After the analysis of the evolution of the temperature during the infusion stage of a thick reinforcement preform, significant differences have been observed depending on the location, both in the longitudinal and through-the-thickness directions. The latter lead us to conclude that for the accurate simulation of resin infusion and curing stages of thick composite parts with vacuum bag, 3D thermal models are required instead of the 2D simulation codes implemented in today software.

There is no clear explanation for the different temperature evolutions observed in the longitudinal direction of the preform although it could be explained by the fact that there is a change in the heat transfer from the hot mould to the cold vacuum bag. For the original vacuumed dry preform, radiation can be expected as the most important heat transfer method. However, once the resin enters the mould and wets the preform, the transfer of heat is mainly due to conduction and convection. Consequently, the heat generated in the mould can be transferred more easily through the resin than through the dry preform, increasing the temperature of the resin. In order to validate this hypothesis and analyse the sensibility of the system to the conductivity and convective effects, infusion could be conducted with resins or thermal fluids for which the heat transfer properties have been accurately determined before the test.

On the other hand, the monotonic increase in temperature, without flat zones or plateaus, for some locations of the preform when reached by the resin flow could be

explained by the exothermic reaction due to the beginning of the cure stage. The repetition of the same tests using a resin without hardener to eliminate the curing effect, together with the infusion tests at room temperature, could help in the clarification of this issue.

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